

**STUDY CONCERNING THE ETHICAL
VALUES PROMOTED BY STUDENTS AT THE END OF
THE SECONDARY SCHOOL CYCLE**

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Abstract

The study investigates the moral values promoted by students at the end of the secondary school cycle in Romania using the Ethical Values Assessment (EVA) questionnaire, focusing on three ethical dimensions: autonomy, community and divinity. The research targeted students in grades 7 and 8, from both rural and urban schools, with attention to differences by grade and participation in extracurricular activities. The results indicate that students generally give high importance to all three ethical dimensions, with Autonomy being the most

important, while Community and Divinity remain strongly supported. Although no statistically significant differences were found between grades or minor descriptive trends were observed. Frequent involvement in extracurricular activities was associated with higher levels of all three ethical dimensions, especially in the areas of autonomy and divinity. These findings highlight the formative potential of extracurricular experiences, the importance of a supportive school climate, and the role of family-school cooperation in promoting moral development. Implications for educational practice include the integration of values into formal and non-formal school curricula, the active involvement of teachers, principals, and families in promoting holistic moral education.

Keywords: moral values, ethical dimensions, adolescence

1. Introduction

Values education is a central dimension of contemporary secondary education, aiming to support students' moral, social and civic development, alongside academic learning. Moral values such as responsibility, respect, cooperation, fairness and empathy play a crucial role in shaping students' behaviour, decision-making and social participation (Albulescu, 2008). In current educational paradigms, schools are increasingly seen not only as spaces where knowledge is shared, but also as environments for character formation and ethical development. Theoretical perspectives on moral development emphasize the progressive nature of the internalization of values during adolescence. Classical theories, such as those proposed by Piaget and Kohlberg (1984), highlight the role of cognitive development and social interaction in the evolution of moral reasoning. According to Kohlberg's (1984) theory, moral development progresses through three levels and six stages, reflecting increasingly autonomous and principled moral reasoning. During adolescence, individuals begin to move beyond conventional morality towards more autonomous moral reasoning (Stan,

2001). More recent educational approaches extend this perspective by recognizing the emotional, relational, and contextual dimensions of moral learning. In this framework, values are understood as dynamic constructs shaped by meaningful experiences, dialogue, and reflection. The contemporary paradigm of moral education is based on the combination of moral knowledge and moral action. At the same time, moral education consists in creating an adequate environment for the internalization of the components of social morality in the structure of the student's personality, leading to the implementation of appropriate moral behavior (Manea, 2014).

Early adolescence, which typically spans the ages of 12 to 14 and corresponds to grades 7 and 8, is a crucial developmental period for the formation and consolidation of moral and social values. This stage is characterized by profound cognitive, emotional, and social transformations that directly influence value orientation of the students, their ethical judgments and behavioral choices (Sion, 2018). At the same time, it is a particularly relevant phase for educational interventions aimed at promoting moral development. Through religious education, students acquire better behavior, including politeness, respect, and helpfulness, reduce radicalism, and their academic performance improves (Khadafie, 2025; Manea, 2019; Virgana & Kasyadi, 2025). From a cognitive perspective, early adolescents experience significant advances in abstract and reflective thinking. The gradual transition from concrete to formal operational thinking allows students to consider hypothetical situations, evaluate multiple perspectives, and engage in more complex moral reasoning (Sanders, 2013). These cognitive changes support the emergence of principled judgment, allowing students to question rules, reflect on fairness and justice, and develop personal value hierarchies. As a result, students in grades 7 and 8 are increasingly able to understand moral concepts beyond simple rule-following. Emotional

development during early adolescence further shapes value formation. Students become more self-aware and sensitive to social evaluation, while emotions such as empathy, guilt, and moral concern take on greater significance. At the same time, emotional regulation is still developing, which can lead to inconsistencies between moral understanding and behavior. Educational contexts that provide opportunities for reflection, dialogue, and emotional engagement play a vital role in supporting the internalization of moral values at this stage. Therefore, active-participatory and reflective-constructive learning is beneficial for desirable student behavior (Albulescu et al. 2021).

At the social level, peer relationships gain increasing importance and exert a strong influence on students' attitudes and behaviors. Adolescents begin to negotiate their identity within peer groups, often balancing the desire for autonomy with the need for belonging. These dynamics can affect value priorities, especially regarding cooperation, conformity, responsibility, and respect for others. Differences between seventh and eighth graders, although subtle, may reflect variations in social maturity and self-concept development, influencing how values are perceived and adopted. In this developmental context, the role of the school becomes particularly significant. Educational practices that encourage discussions about ethical dilemmas, collaborative learning, and real-life problem solving can encourage moral reflection and value clarification. Transdisciplinary pedagogical approaches are particularly well-suited for early adolescence because they integrate moral learning with cognitive and social experiences across domains (Baumber, 2022). By addressing authentic issues and encouraging students to connect knowledge with ethical considerations, such approaches support the holistic development of moral values. Given the developmental sensitivity of early adolescence, systematic assessment of students' value orientations is essential for understanding how moral values

evolve during this stage. Tools such as the EVA questionnaire provide valuable information about students' attitudes and perceptions, allowing educators and researchers to identify developmental trends and contextual influences. In this sense, early adolescence represents both a critical window for moral development and a strategic target for educational research and intervention.

Educational context is a significant factor shaping adolescents' school experiences, academic achievement, and opportunities for personal and moral development (Măirean & Maftai, 2024). In Romania, wide socio-economic disparities between rural and urban areas contribute to persistent inequalities in education that extend from early childhood to secondary education and beyond. Large-scale reports and empirical studies show that students in rural communities face multiple structural challenges that differentiate their educational trajectories from those of their urban peers. For example, OECD data indicate that students in rural areas are less likely to participate in early childhood education and care, have lower academic achievement in key areas such as mathematics, and face higher school dropout rates compared to urban students, with rural secondary school completion rates being considerably lower than in urban settings (OECD, 2025)⁷. Socio-economic factors also shape the educational environment and the processes of value formation (Mikó & Hatos, 2024). The aim of ethics education is to develop cognitive capacities and critical thinking skills that allow individuals to identify the ethical dimensions of problems and to reflect/address these problems by minimizing any negative effects. However, the complexity of education from a curricular perspective often generates less space for moral or ethical education in schools (Sivasubramaniam, 2023). Quantitative assessment of values plays a crucial role in advancing empirical research in value education and moral development. Although values are inherently complex and context-dependent, quantitative methods allow researchers to systematically

operationalize these constructs, identify patterns, and examine relationships between values and educational variables such as age, school context, and learning environment. (Schwartz, 2006; Chrostowski, 2022). In the context of adolescence, where value systems are still forming and undergoing rapid transformation, quantitative measurements provide a structured means of capturing developmental trends and differences that may not be readily observable through qualitative methods alone (Eisenberg et al. 2006). Furthermore, quantitative assessment supports statistical analysis of value dimensions, facilitating the identification of correlations, group differences, and potential predictors of value orientation. Such evidence is essential for evaluating the effectiveness of educational approaches—such as transdisciplinary pedagogy—and for informing evidence-based educational policies and practices. While quantitative approaches may not capture the full depth of individual moral experiences, they provide a necessary basis for systematic inquiry and can be effectively complemented by qualitative methods within mixed-methods research designs (Cohen et al., 2018).

2. Research coordinates

2.1. Purpose and Hypotheses

The purpose of the study is to investigate the moral values promoted by Romanian middle school students on three dimensions: autonomy, community, and divinity.

Regarding the hypotheses, it was assumed that middle school students would give greater importance to values associated with autonomy than to those related to community and divinity, reflecting the developmental emphasis on self-direction and personal responsibility during early adolescence. Second, it was hypothesized that seventh graders would score higher on values oriented toward community and divinity than eighth graders, given potential age-related changes in moral

priorities. Another hypothesis concerns students' participation in extracurricular activities, assuming that frequent involvement would be associated with higher levels of values related to autonomy, community, and divinity, compared to occasional participation or non-participation. Finally, it was hypothesized that the three ethical dimensions would be positively correlated, indicating that adolescents tend to value autonomy, community, and divinity simultaneously, rather than considering them as competing moral orientations.

2.2. Instrument and methodology

The questionnaire has been administered online, as a Google Forms form, with completion being a voluntary act with guaranteed anonymity. The instrument used was the EVA (Ethical Values Assessment) questionnaire, in its 18-item version developed by Jensen, L.A. (2018), validated by Nicoară, D. R. (2023), which is a standardized instrument designed to assess value orientations by capturing three distinct ethical frameworks: Community, Autonomy and Divinity. The items are structured to reflect situations and dilemmas relevant to students' everyday experiences, encouraging responses based on practical decision-making rather than abstract theory. This ensures that the instrument captures adolescents' value orientations as they are put into practice in real-life social and educational contexts, rather than reflecting only hypothetical judgments. Each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important), indicating the perceived importance of each value to the respondent. The instrument comprises three subscales, each consisting of six items. The Autonomy Ethics subscale assesses values related to personal responsibility, self-care, self-satisfaction, goal orientation, fairness, and respect for individual rights (e.g., taking responsibility for one's own actions; striving to achieve personal goals; respecting the rights of others). The Community Ethics subscale measures values associated with responsibility to

family and society, cooperation, social roles, and the pursuit of social harmony (e.g., caring for one’s family; being a cooperative member of society; fulfilling responsibilities toward others). The Divinity Ethics subscale focuses on religious and spiritual values, including care for the soul, spiritual guidance, and adherence to divine or transcendent principles (e.g., caring for one’s own soul; self-guidance through a spiritual life). By measuring the ethics of Community, Autonomy, and Divinity, the EVA provides a nuanced picture of how adolescents navigate moral complexity, balancing personal conscience, social obligations, and cultural or spiritual principles (Jensen, 2015). The sample of participants consisted in seventh and eighth grade students, from both rural and urban backgrounds, from BN County, Romania.

2.3. Results

Below we present the scores recorded at the level of the two groups: grades 7 and 8 in terms of positioning towards the three ethical dimensions measured: autonomy, community and divinity (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Comparative Scores on Ethical Dimensions

Analyzing the recorded data, it is found that the average scores for all three ethical dimensions were in the upper range of the scale (above 4), which

indicates that students generally considered the values related to autonomy, community and divinity to be important or very important. At the individual level, most students manifested autonomy as a dominant ethical orientation, continuing to support the importance of values related to autonomy in early adolescence. As a positioning, the autonomy dimension obtained the highest average score, followed by community and divinity, which confirms the first hypothesis, namely that middle school students give greater importance to values associated with autonomy than to those related to community and divinity. Comparisons between seventh and eighth grade students revealed slightly higher average scores for seventh grade students in all three ethical dimensions. However, the differences were not statistically significant for autonomy, community, or divinity, although a descriptive trend suggested that seventh graders placed somewhat more importance on community and spiritual values. Therefore, the hypothesis that marked the age/grade difference (seventh graders show a greater orientation than eighth graders towards community and divinity) was not statistically confirmed.

With reference to the implications that participation in extracurricular activities has on students' subsequent orientation towards the three measured dimensions (autonomy, community, divinity), the recorded data are summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Scores on Ethical Dimensions in relation to participation in extra-curricular activities

Participation in extracurricular activities was significantly associated with students' ethical orientations. Students who reported frequent involvement in extracurricular activities scored higher on all three ethical dimensions, especially autonomy and divinity. Statistical analyses indicated significant differences for autonomy and divinity and a nonsignificant trend for community. Post hoc comparisons revealed that frequently involved students scored higher than those who participated occasionally or not at all, while no relevant differences were found between occasional participants and nonparticipants. These findings support our hypothesis (frequent involvement in extracurricular activities is associated with higher levels of values related to autonomy, community, and divinity, compared to occasional participation or nonparticipation) and suggest that sustained involvement in extracurricular activities is related to stronger endorsement of ethical values during early adolescence.

Regarding the hypothesis advanced regarding the degree of correlation (the three ethical dimensions: autonomy, community and divinity are positively correlated) it is confirmed, as the results indicate the correlations between the three ethical dimensions as being large and positive, which implies that autonomy, community and divinity are not mutually exclusive, but coexist, so to speak, students tend to appreciate them simultaneously.

3. Discussions

The results obtained by applying the EVA questionnaire indicate a complex value profile of the student at the end of the secondary school cycle in which the three ethical dimensions: autonomy, community and divinity are strongly supported, with a slight predominance of the dimension targeting

autonomy. The only factor that generated notable differences in ethical orientations was frequent participation in extracurricular activities. We interpret the above data in terms of the fact that secondary school students attribute a high level of importance to all three ethical-moral orientations assessed by the EVA instrument. The values related to autonomy, community and divinity were generally assessed as important or very important, with autonomy appearing as the most prominent ethical orientation, on average. However, this predominance does not occur at the expense of the other two dimensions, suggesting a balanced system of moral values, rather than a unidimensional ethical focus. The analyses did not reveal substantial differences in ethical orientations depending on the grade level, although minor descriptive variations were observed - such as slightly higher values oriented towards community and divinity among seventh graders. These results suggest a relative homogeneity of moral value endorsement within the studied sample. In contrast, participation in extracurricular activities emerged as a significant differentiating factor, in that students who reported frequent involvement in extracurricular activities demonstrated higher levels of all three ethical orientations, especially autonomy and divinity. This finding highlights the formative potential of structured extracurricular involvement in supporting adolescents' moral development and internalization of values beyond the formal curriculum. Finally, the strong positive correlations observed between autonomy, community, and divinity indicate the presence of an integrated moral profile in early adolescence. Rather than functioning as competing ethical orientations, the three dimensions appear to reinforce each other, suggesting that adolescents who value personal responsibility and self-direction also tend to emphasize social responsibility and spiritual or transcendental concerns. These findings have several important educational implications for schools, teachers, school counselors, and educational policymakers. One of the most important indicators

of a society's maturity and sustainability is its capacity to articulate and translate into practice an educational system capable of capitalizing on the educational potential offered by the heterogeneity of its structure (Stan & Manea, 2018).

The significant role of extracurricular activities highlighted by the results underlines their formative potential in values education. Participation in structured extracurricular activities has been associated with higher levels of responsibility, cooperation and self-regulation among adolescents (Mahoney et al. 2005). Frequent participation in such activities appears to provide meaningful contexts in which students can exercise autonomy, take responsibility, cooperate with others and engage in shared values beyond the formal classroom setting. Therefore, educational institutions are encouraged to diversify and actively promote extracurricular programs, such as clubs, sports teams, volunteer initiatives, cultural projects and student organizations, as integral components of moral and civic education, rather than as optional additions to academic learning. By promoting dialogue, modeling ethical behavior, and supporting students' moral decision-making, educators (teachers, school administrators) can significantly contribute to the development of a coherent and supportive moral environment. Hence the importance of the broader school climate in shaping students' ethical orientations. The National Research Council (NRC), part of the National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) (2004) in the United States, concluded that the environment and community contexts contribute to students' engagement and motivational development, which in turn influence the internalization of values.

It is worth noting that effective moral education requires ongoing cooperation between school and family. Families play a central role in the early transmission of values, while schools provide structured opportunities for reflection, practice, and social learning. Strengthening partnerships between

teachers, school counselors, and parents can enhance the coherence of moral messages received by students and support their ethical development in different contexts (Bierman & Sheridan, 2022). Therefore, future educational initiatives could benefit from more active involvement of families in projects, discussions, and extracurricular activities related to values. Future research could further explore the mechanisms through which extracurricular involvement and school climate influence moral development, as well as examine longitudinal changes in ethical orientations across adolescence. Expanding the sample and incorporating qualitative approaches could also provide deeper insights into how students interpret and integrate autonomy, community, and divinity into their lived experiences.

4. Conclusions

The students involved in this research already demonstrate a strong orientation towards the values of autonomy, community and divinity; the central educational challenge is to promote the transformation of these values into stable attitudes and consistent behaviors. This process requires sustained opportunities for lived experience, the presence of coherent ethical models and the creation of meaningful learning contexts that allow students to reflect on moral principles and put them into practice in everyday educational contexts. Attachment to values such as: love, truth, respect, responsibility is formed over time as a result of their cultivation, of achieving a healthy, sustainable education for the world and life (Manea et al. 2004). Therefore, moral education should not be approached as an isolated curricular component, but rather as a transversal dimension integrated into both school and extracurricular activities.

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